

(methanol) on a Specord Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer, mass spectra on a JEOLJMS-DX 300 spectrometer and nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Perkin-Elmer R-35 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard. All the melting points are uncorrected. Compounds were routinely checked for their purity on silica gel-G tic plates.

1-Aminophenyl-1,3-butanedione-2-arylhydrazones (1): The required derivatives of aromatic amine (0.05 mol) were dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid (12.5 ml) and water (12.5 ml). The mixture was cooled to 0° in an ice-salt-bath. To it sodium nitrite solution (3.50 g, 0.05 mol), cooled to 0° , was added in small portions. The diazonium salt so obtained was filtered into cooled mixture of sodium acetate (25.00 g in 100 ml ethanol) and reactive methylene compound (0.05 mol); 1-aminophenyl-1,3-butanedione and 1-amino(2-chlorophenyl)-1,3-butanedione for synthesising compounds sl. nos. 1–16 and 17–31 respectively (Table 1). The resulting solid products were washed with water and recrystallised from 50% DMF–water mixture, m.p. 110° (Found: N, 14.50. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: N, 14.94%); λ_{max} (MeOH) 390 nm; M^+ at m/e 281.

2-Arylazo-1-aminophenyl-1,3-butanedione (2): The aromatic amine (0.025 mol) dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid (6.5 ml) and water (6.5 ml), was cooled to 0° in an ice-salt-bath. To it sodium nitrite solution (1.75 g, 0.025 mol) cooled to 0° was added in small portions. The diazonium salt so obtained was filtered into cooled mixture of 10% NaOH in 50% ethanol–water mixture containing reactive methylene compound (0.025 mol); 1-aminophenyl-1,3-butanedione and 1-amino(2-chlorophenyl)-1,3-butanedione for synthesising compounds sl. nos. 1–15 and 16–30 respectively (Table 2). The resulting solid products were washed thoroughly with water and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 90° (Found: N, 14.6. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ calcd. for: N, 14.9%); λ_{max} (CH_3OH) 400 nm; M^+ at m/e 281; ν_{max} (KBr) 1605 (N=N), 3440 (NH CO $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}$), 1680 (C=O) and 830–690 cm^{-1} (substituted phenyl); δ (CDCl_3) 2.32 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.6 (s, CH), 6.95–7.10 (1H, m, 2 aromatic ring) and 1.51 (1H, CONH).

1-Carbamoyl-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-arylazo-pyrazoles (3): To 1-aminophenyl-1,3-butanedione-2-arylhydrazone (0.004 mol) dissolved in ethanol (50 ml), a hot solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.004 mol) in alcohol was added and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. On cooling, the resulting shining crystals were recrystallised from water–DMF mixture, m.p. 125° (Found: N, 25.90. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_6\text{O}$ calcd. for: N, 26.25%); λ_{max} (CH_3OH) 410 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 1600 (N=N), 3450 (NH), 1660 (C=C or C=N), 850 (phenyl), 1690 cm^{-1} (–CO– of –CONH₂), do not show any peak for the hydrogen bonded C=O or acetyl CO, thereby confirming structure (3) for these compounds; δ (CDCl_3) 2.02 (1H, NH), 2.4 (3H, CH_3), 7–8.10 (10H, two phenyl rings) and 8.2 (2H, NH_2).

Similarly, other 1-carbamoyl-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles were prepared by taking suitably substituted 1-aminophenyl-1,3-butanedione-2-arylhydrazone and 1-amino(2-chlorophenyl)-1,3-butanedione (Table 3).

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Pyrimidine Antagonists. Part-II. Synthesis of some 2,4-Diamino-5-arylazo-6-(substituted-amino)pyrimidines and Studies of their Anticancer Activity

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PURINE and pyrimidine derivatives¹ exhibits antagonistic activity on nucleic acid metabolism and reveal various biological activities. The 2,4-diamino pyrimidine moiety is responsible for binding of the compounds at the active site of an enzyme for which folic acid acts as a substrate². In continuation of the synthesis of pyridine derivatives³, the present paper reports the synthesis of some new 2,4-diamino-6-substituted-amino-5-arylazopyrimidines and the biological activity of the compounds.

The new 5-arylazopyrimidines (2) were synthesised by the reaction of an appropriate 2,4-diamino-6-substituted-aminopyrimidines (1) with diazotised

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arylamine at 0–10° at pH 3–4, 5–7 or 8–9 depending on the nature of 1 used. The compounds were crystallised from appropriate solvents. The 5-arylazopyrimidines are soluble in ethanol, methanol, acetone, pyridine and ethylacetate but insoluble in benzene, toluene and ether at room temperature.

HIV-activity evaluation on human host cell of some of the selected compounds by National Cancer Institute, USA are in progress.

The arylazopyrimidines having an arylamino group at C-6 position showed strong uv absorption at 274–292 nm and those having saturated amino group at C-6 position showed at 240–275 nm. All the compounds exhibited a high intensity band at 386–442 nm. Ir spectra of all the compounds revealed identical bands at 2 800–3 400 (NH), 1 680–1 640 (C=N pyrimidine), 1 630–1 575 (N=N), 1 667–1 429 (four bands, C=C Ar), 1 360–1 250 (CN amines) and 780–680 cm⁻¹ (subs. benz.).

Different compounds showed characteristic bands due to different substituted groups. (Table 1).

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in capillary tubes on an aluminium block and are uncorrected.

In crystallisation aqueous 95% (v/v) ethanol was used. Uv spectra of the compounds were determined on a Shimadzu 210A spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr/nujol) on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer.

General methods of preparation of 5-arylazopyrimidines (2) : To a suspension of 2,4-trisubstituted-pyrimidine* (0.004 mol) in water (200 ml), glacial-acetic acid (10–20 ml) was added dropwise with stirring until a clear solution was obtained. 2,4-Diamino-6-*p*-sulphoanilopyrimidine and 2,4-diamino-6-*p*-carboxyanilopyrimidine were dissolved in 10 N NaOH (10 ml) with constant stirring, 2,4-diamino-6-*p*-nitroanilopyrimidine was dissolved in 10 N HCl (10 ml). The solution was cooled in ice-water and an ice-cold solution of an equimolar amount of the diazotised arylamine (prepared by adding a cold solution of 0.004 mol NaNO₂ in 10 ml water with stirring to an ice-cold solution of 0.004 mol amine in 20 ml 1 N HCl; the diazotised solution containing excess of HCl) was added slowly with stirring (5 min). Then 1 N NaOH solution was added to it dropwise to bring the pH of the solution to 8–9 when precipitate for compounds 2 (sl. nos. 1, 3, 4 and 12) appeared. In case of compounds sl. nos. 16, 5, 7, 8, 11 and 26, a coloured solution was obtained instead of precipitate. 1 N HCl was added dropwise to obtain heavy precipitate at pH 3–4 and stirring continued for 4 h. In case of compounds sl. nos. 2, 6, 9, 13, 14, 15, 17, 18, 19 and 22, pH was adjusted to 3–4 by adding 2 N HCl or 2 N NaOH and stirring continued for 4 h to yield heavy precipitate of the products. Instead of precipitate coloured solution was obtained for compounds sl. nos. 20, 21, 24 and 28 and its pH was adjusted to

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 5-ARYLAZOPYRIMIDINES (2)*

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	Mol. formula	Yield %	Colour (Nature)	M.p.** °C	λ _{max} † nm	ν _{max} cm ⁻¹
1.	OC ₂ H ₅	Br	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ BrN ₇ O	98	Brownish orange (Plate)	165d ^b	282s, 400l, 425, 440l	1 070 (OC ₂ H ₅), 540 (Br)
2.	OC ₂ H ₅	I	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ IN ₇ O	80	Brown (Crystal)	210d ^b	280s, 390br, 485l	1 144 (OC ₂ H ₅), 495 (I)
3.	OC ₂ H ₅	OC ₂ H ₅	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₇ O ₂	98	Canary yellow (Crystal)	220 ^b	288, 392, 430	1 071, 1 115, 1 148 (OC ₂ H ₅)
4.	OC ₂ H ₅	OOH ₂	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ N ₇ O ₂	99	Brownish yellow (Crystal)	165d ^a	255, 292, 395s, 390l, 412l	1 070 (OC ₂ H ₅), 1 040 (OOH ₂)
5.	COOH	Br	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ BrN ₇ O ₂	70	Deep brown (Crystal)	210 ^b	280, 300s, 432vl, 486l	2 900 (COOH), 1 680 (CO), 550 (Br)
6.	COOH	I	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ IN ₇ O ₂	80	Brownish yellow (Crystal)	290d ^a	265, 355s, 400, 435, 485	2 843 (COOH), 1 698 (CO), 486 (I)
7.	COOH	OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₇ O ₂	25	Deep brown (Powder)	180d ^a	260, 308s, 396l, 432	2 900 (COOH), 1 680 (CO), 1 120 (OC ₂ H ₅)

NOTES

(Table 1 contd.)

8.	COOH	OCH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₇ O ₂	60	Deep brown (Crystal)	122-25d ^b	290, 307, 355, 390, 440i	2 834 (COOH), 1 673 (CO), 1 087 (OCH ₃)
9.	SO ₂ NH ₂	Br	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ BrN ₆ SO ₂	50	Dull yellow (Crystal)	320-25d ^a	268i, 300s, 345, 395, 430	1 327, 1 142 (SO ₂ NH ₂), 594 (Br)
10.	SO ₂ NH ₂	I	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ IN ₆ SO ₂	82	Deep brown (Crystal)	180 ^b	283s, 342br, 402vi, 487	1 327, 1 138 (SO ₂ NH ₂), 500 (I)
11.	SO ₂ NH ₂	OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₆ SO ₂	75	Brownish yellow (Crystal)	150d ^a	270vi, 302s, 399, 430br, 485	1 346, 1 145 (SO ₂ NH ₂), 1 113 (OC ₂ H ₅)
12.	SO ₂ NH ₂	OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ SO ₂	50	Reddish brown (Needle)	190 ^b	300s, 395, 430	1 290, 1 142 (SO ₂ NH ₂), 1 142 (OCH ₃)
13.	SO ₂ H	Br	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ BrN ₇ SO ₂	60	Yellow (Plate)	300d ^a	255, 286, 315, 400	1 194, 1 032, 640 (SO ₂ H), 568 (Br)
14.	SO ₂ H	I	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ IN ₇ SO ₂	82	Deep brown (Crystal)	205d ^b	265s, 298s, 315i, 362i, 425i	1 164, 1 028, 640 (SO ₂ H), 505 (I)
15.	SO ₂ H	OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₇ SO ₄	82	Snuff (Powder)	150d ^a	260s, 295, 312s, 375vi, 433	1 139, 1 064, 625 (SO ₂ H), 1 087 (OC ₂ H ₅)
16.	SO ₂ H	OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₇ SO ₄	70	Brownish yellow (Crystal)	225d ^b	298, 308s, 360, 432i	1 197, 1 021, 666 (SO ₂ H), 1 149 (OCH ₃)
17.	NO ₂	Br	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ BrN ₆ O ₂	90	Golden yellow (Needle)	225 ^b	250s, 265vi, 315, 365, 360br	1 582, 1 371 (NO ₂), 500 (Br)
18.	NO ₂	I	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ IN ₆ O ₂	68	Shiney orange (Needle)	280 ^a	230i, 283, 365s	1 540, 1 320 (NO ₂), 520 (I)
19.	NO ₂	OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₆ O ₂	98	Deep brown (Crystal)	180 ^a	255i, 296i, 395	1 537, 1 371 (NO ₂), 1 103, 1 137 (OC ₂ H ₅)
20.	NO ₂	OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂	78	Fine yellow (Needle)	145 ^b	263, 285, 312, 390	1 569, 1 302 (NO ₂), 1 063, 1 145 (OCH ₃)
21.	Br	Br	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₇ ^c	60	Yellow (Plate)	241-47d ^b	295, 342, 390, 425i	500 (Br)
22.	Br	I	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ BrIN ₇	90	Brownish yellow (Powder)	200-05d ^a	296s, 322i, 395, 440	518 (Br), 500 (I)
23.	Br	OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ BrN ₇ O	70	Dull yellow (Plate)	235d ^a	295, 305, 345i, 390	560 (Br), 1 080 (OC ₂ H ₅)
24.	Br	OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ BrN ₇ O	40	Deep brown (Crystal)	200d ^a	296s, 308, 340i, 380br, 425vi	518 (Br), 1 168, 1 070 (OCH ₃)
25.	Cl	Br	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ BrClN ₇	78	Orange (Crystal)	242 ^b	262i, 292s, 340, 390, 430i	669, 785 (Cl), 480 (Br)
26.	Cl	I	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ BrIN ₇	90	Canary yellow (Crystal)	245 ^b	206s, 286s, 340, 400, 425	785, 720 (Cl), 500 (I)
27.	Cl	OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ ClN ₇ O	98	Dull yellow (Crystal)	252d ^b	305, 315vi, 342i, 390, 425	785 (Cl), 1 112, 1 087 (OC ₂ H ₅)
28.	Cl	OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ClN ₇ O	98	Dull yellow (Crystal)	205 ^b	260vi, 290, 340, 390	786, 815 (Cl), 1 086, 1 150 (OCH ₃)

*Satisfactory C, H and N analyses obtained.

**Solvent used for crystallisation : ^aethanol, ^baqueous ethanol.

†Nature of band : s=sharp, br=board, i=inconspicuous vi=very inconspicuous.

^cTurns green when kept in open air for about three months due to air oxidation.

8-9 by adding 2 N NaOH to get heavy precipitate of the products. Coloured solution was also obtained in case of compounds sl. nos. 23 and 27, when pH was adjusted to 6-7 to get maximum precipitate. In case of compounds sl. nos. 10 and 25, pH was maintained at 6-7 by adding 2 N HCl

or 2 N NaOH and stirring continued further for 4 h when heavy precipitate appeared. A temperature of 0-10° was maintained throughout the reaction. The reaction mixture was then kept in a refrigerator for 12 h. The crude product was filtered, washed with water, dried at 80° and purified by crystallisation.

Antitumour screening : The antitumour screening of the compounds 2 (sl. nos. 4, 5, 13, 16 and 27) were carried out at National Cancer Institute, USA, against Murine lymphocytic leukemia P-388 according to the standard method⁴ in BDF₁ mice. Ip administration of compounds began 24 h after the inoculation of 1×10^6 P-388 cells in BDF₁ mice and performed once daily for 1–7 days. Vehicle used was saline, saline with tween 80. The compounds were tested at dose levels 100, 200 and 400 mg/kg. The compounds did not show significant antitumour activity. The best T/C value (104%) shown as by compound sl. no. 13 (T/C \geq 120 is considered active).

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Synthesis of 5-(3,5-Dinitrophenyl)-3-[(substituted-amino)methyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione as Potential Biological Active Agents

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THE oxadiazoles possess various biological activities¹. Hence, it was considered of interest to synthesise the title compounds and to evaluate their antibacterial and antiviral activities. 3,5-Dinitrophenylhydrazine was heated with carbon disulphide and potassium hydroxide in absolute alcohol to yield 5-(3,5-dinitrophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione (1), which was then subjected to Mannich reaction to yield 5-(3,5-dinitrophenyl)-3-[(substituted-amino)methyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-

thione (2). The biological activity of the compounds (2) was evaluated.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra were recorded using TMS as internal standard.

5-(3,5-Dinitrophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione (1) : It was prepared by the reported method².

5-(3,5-Dinitrophenyl)-3-(substituted-amino)methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione (2) : A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and formalin (0.02 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (25 ml) for 1 h. A secondary amine (0.01 mol) was then added to it and further refluxed for 4–6 h. The excess of ethanol was distilled off, cooled and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from methanol, (2; 50–60%); 2c: m.p. 245° (Found : C, 42.73 ; H, 3.80 ; N, 19.59. C₁₈H₁₃N₅O₆S calcd. for : C, 42.50 ; H, 3.54 ; N, 19.08%) ; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 645 (C=N), 1 170 (C=S), 1 590 (Ar), 1 300 (NO₂) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=C phenyl) ; δ (CDCl₃) 2.38 (2H, s, CH₃), 2.1 (4H, m, CH₂NCH₂ of morpholine) and 7.2 (3H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds of the series were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (2)*

Compd. no.	NR	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
2a	Methylpiperazino	180	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₆ S
2b	Phenylpiperazino	210	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆ S
2c	Morpholino	245	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₆ S
2d	Piperidino	260	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₆ S
2e	Diethylamino	235	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₆ S
2f	Dimethylamino	120	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₆ S
2g	Pyrolidino	194	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₆ S
2h	Diphenylamino	140	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₆ S
2i	Succinimido	175	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₅ O ₆ S
2j	Phthalimido	198	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₆ O ₇ S

*Satisfactory C, H and N obtained for all compounds.

Biological activity : Antibacterial activity of the compounds was evaluated by agar plate diffusion technique³ against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* using tetracycline as standard. 2b was found to be most active while the others showed moderate activity. Antiviral activity was tested⁴ against *Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* (CT) for Sunnhemp Rosette virus (SRV). All the compounds exhibited activity in the range 30–63%.